

EFFECT OF AGE GROUPS ON THE PREFERENCES TOWARDS ULIPS

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Abstract

Purpose: ULIP stands for unit linked insurance plans. ULIP is a combination of insurance and investment. Here policyholder can pay a premium monthly or annually. A small amount of the premium goes to secure life insurance and rest of the money is invested just like a mutual fund does. Policyholder goes on investing through the term of the policy – 5, 10 or 15 years and accumulates the units. ULIP offers investors options that invest in equity and debt. An aggressive investor can pick equity oriented fund option whereas a conservative one can go with debt option.

In ULIPSs the investors can choose their portfolio, called the fund option, where their money would be invested, usually the insurance company offers Growth Fund-that is Equity share oriented, Balanced Fund-Which is a combination of Debt and, and Income Fund-which is Debt fund oriented.

The investors have a numbers of benefits from ULIPs viz. Higher Returns, Tax Saving, Wealth Creation, Investment, Flexibility, Liquidity, Professional Fund Management, Top-up Facility , saving, and Pension.

Out of these benefits, investors found Higher Returns, Tax saving, Wealth Creation and Investment as their key preferences due to which they purchase ULIPs. Also Age of the investors also affects the preferences of ULIPs.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The study is based on the responses gathered through structured questionnaires. The convenient sampling has been used. Sample size of 140 respondents from Delhi NCR region who have Life insurance policy of LIC/and Birla Sun Life Insurance.

Findings- Out of the various benefits from ULIPs , the investors found Higher Returns, Tax saving, Wealth Creation and Investment as their key preferences due to which they purchase ULIPs. Also Age of the investors also affects the preferences of ULIPs.

Limitations- The study has been conducted in Delhi NCR region and the sample are 140, so the results may not hold apt on pan India bases.

Practical Implications: As found in the study that Higher Returns, Tax Saving Benefits, Wealth Creation and Investment are the key benefits which motivate investors to buy ULIPs, the insurance companies must design some products which give maximum benefit in a single ULIP.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical aspects ULIP, and the companies which are following modern marketing tactics in innovating ULIPs and also includes literature review about the various aspects of ULIPs.

Key words: Unit Linked Insurance Plans, Policy-holder, Portfolio, Growth Fund, Balanced Fund , Income Fund, Pension

INTRODUCTION

Insurance is a means of protection from financial loss. It is a form of risk management primarily used to hedge against the risk of a contingent, uncertain loss. Insurance may be described as a social device to reduce or eliminate risk of life and property. Under the plan of insurance, a large number of people associate themselves by sharing risk, attached to individual.

Unit Linked Insurance Plan (ULIP) provides for life insurance where the policy value at any time varies according to the value of the underlying assets at the time. ULIP is life insurance solution that provides for the benefits of protection and flexibility in investment. The investment is denoted as units and is represented by the value that it has attained called as Net Asset Value (NAV).ULIP came into play in the 1960s and is popular in many countries in the world. The reason that is attributed to the wide spread popularity of ULIP is because of the transparency and the flexibility which it offers. As times progressed the plans were also successfully mapped along with life insurance need to retirement planning. In today's times, ULIP provides solutions for insurance planning, financial needs, financial planning for children's marriage planning etc., Unit Linked Insurance Plan - is a financial product that offers you life insurance as well as an investment like a mutual fund. Part of the premium you pay goes towards the sum assured (amount you get in a life insurance policy) and the balance will be invested in whichever investments you desire - equity, fixed-return or a mixture of both. In India Insurance Regulatory Development Authority(IRDA) on the recent regulations 1st September 2010 states that the following changes such as Increasing cap on various charges, change in the lock in period from 3

to 5 years and the assured return has been stated as 4.5%.Hence there is a need to understand the consumer perception.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

With the increase in domestic savings and improvement in awareness of value of life of the earning person in a family, the need and scope for life Insurance operation has increased tremendously. Life Insurance are not only best suited for the purpose of insuring the life but also are capable of meeting future financial challenges effectively. Hence, this study explores about the customers' perception and awareness level of Unit Linked Insurance Policy (ULIP).

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

To study the demographic and rational profile of customers of ULIP To study the Customers' Perception towards ULIP To identify those factors which develops a favorable opinion among consumers towards ULIP. To see the effect of age on the preferences of ULIPs.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Unit Linked Insurance Policies [ULIP] was first offered in the United States in 1976, [after being developed and sold successfully in The Netherlands, England, and Canada] in the name of Variable Life Insurance. Basically it was a type of whole life insurance whose values may vary directly with the performance of a set of earmarked investments. A plan which gives complete clarity about the various charges deducted and why it's being deducted and so how your fund will grow over time. Unit Linked Insurance Policies (ULIPs) as an investment avenue are closest to mutual funds in terms of their structure and functioning. As is the case with mutual funds, investors in ULIPs is allotted units by the insurance company and a net asset value (NAV) is declared for the same on a daily basis. Similarly ULIP investors have the option of investing across various schemes similar to the ones found in the mutual funds domain, i.e. diversified equity funds, balanced funds and debt funds to name a few. Generally speaking, ULIPs can be termed as mutual fund schemes with an insurance component. However it should not be construed that barring the insurance element there is nothing differentiating mutual funds from ULIPs. ULIPs are a category of goal-based financial solutions that combine the safety of insurance protection with wealth creation opportunities. In ULIPs, a part of the investment goes

towards providing you life cover. The residual portion of the ULIP is invested in a fund which in turn invests in stocks or bonds; the value of investments alters with the performance of the underlying fund opted by you. Simply to put in nutshell, ULIPs are structured in such a way that the protection element and the savings element are distinguishable, and hence managed according to your specific needs. In this way, the ULIP plan offers unprecedented flexibility and transparency.

WORKING OF ULIPS

It is critical that you understand how your money gets invested once you purchase a ULIP: When you decide the amount of premium to be paid and the amount of life cover you want from the ULIP, the insurer deducts some portion of the ULIP premium upfront. This portion is known as the Premium Allocation charge, and varies from product to product. The rest of the premium is invested in the fund or mixture of funds chosen by you. Mortality charges and ULIP administration charges are thereafter deducted on a periodic (mostly monthly) basis by cancellation of units, whereas the ULIP fund management charges are adjusted from NAV on a daily basis. Since the fund of your choice has an underlying investment – either in equity or debt or a combination of the two – your fund value will reflect the performance of the underlying asset classes. At the time of maturity of your plan, you are entitled to receive the fund value as at the time of maturity.

Unit linked plans provide an opportunity for the discerning investor to benefit from the return available in their capital market without going for direct investments in capital market half yearly or yearly. Out of the premium amounts, deductions will be made towards Initial administrative charges like, Investment management charges [there will be an extra charge if the policyholder utilizes the switch over (from equity to debt or debt to balance) option], Annual administration charges, Risk cover and the balance will be invested in a selected fund [debt or equity or balance]. In case of death during the premium paying term or the term of the policy, the sum assured [Rs.1 Lakh in example] or value of policy fund, whichever is higher, is paid to the beneficiaries. In case of survival up to maturity, the value of the fund is paid out. The returns on that day [maturity or death] on the plan depend upon the performance of the market, be it equity or debt. So if the fund value falls below amount invested on that day, the policyholder will

receive a lesser amount. Hence one can see that the risk here is transferred to the policyholder as nothing is guaranteed. The Net Asset Value [NAV] will reflect the underlying value of assets, which in turn is dependent on the movement of the Sensex.

According to Agarwal(2010), ULIP helps to manage the risk return profile. With the double advantage of security and investment, ULIPs have become the most popular insurance product from the available range of life insurance policies. With a higher rate of return, ULIPs gives tough competition to traditional insurance products like endowment plans and money back plans. The basic reason for opting for policies other than the term insurance is ensuring highest maturity value for invested sum besides mortality benefits. In maturity value the important factors to be considered is the internal rate of return (IRR) on investment. IRDA has fixed 6% and 10% as the assumed rate of return for projecting future benefits. The general rule for Debt-Equity portfolio management in ULIPs is that you should go conservative by increasing your investment in debt when the markets are at their highest, very unstable and likely to start falling any time. Vice versa when the markets are very low and depressed. [1] . Dipak Mondal (2010) The minimum sum assured (life cover) in Ulips is five times and most policies offer cover between 5-10 times the annual premium which has been the signaling factor for the investors [2] Amar ranu (2010), leading financial conglomerate says that other market related products lags behind ULIPs return by a larger margin in the long term which confirms that investment in ULIPs are ideal investment vehicle for wealth creation in long run. ULIP score over other products in terms of returns and additional benefits such as insurance cover. However it scores below PPF as investment in ULIPs involves high risks. [3] . ULIPs are covered under sec 80(C), 10 10(D) of IT Act, hence tax benefits up to a maximum of Rs.1,00,000 investment can claimed in these plans.(Sanjay Mathew,2010) [4] . As per the news published on business line on Monday, December 13, 2010 the changes made by IRDA on ULIP includes the top-up premium. IRDA said adding all limited premium ULIPs, other than single premium products, shall have premium paying term of at least five years. The premium has also gone up to 10 times of the year premium compared to existing 5 times. All ULIP pension or annuity products will offer a minimum guaranteed return of 4.5% per annum or as specified by the IRDA from time to time. [5]. According to Suddhadeb Chakraborti(2010), financial consultant and author discuss about

the latest amendments that it provides mortality health cover in which it has been made mandatory to have Mortality Health Cover for all ULIPS apart from Pension and Annuity schemes. No partial withdrawal is available under new ULIPS. This enables a person to stay invested and hence protect his corpus. A guaranteed return of 4.5% has been announced to keep investors happy. [6]

Features /BENEFITS FROM ULIP
Higher Expected Return than Traditional Plans
TAX Saving
Wealth Creation
ULIPs are Insurance cum Investment Instrument
Flexibility in choosing Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option
Liquidity: Option to withdraw/partial withdraw the Fund Value
Professional Fund Management or Fund is managed properly.
Top-up option: Option to Invest additional in the same Policy
Top up option-Option to invest additional amount in the same policy
Saving for Special Reason like Children Education/Marriage
Pension

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research is used. The sampling method is non probability purposive sampling. In that, the sample is chosen so that a particular research purpose is served and is adequate for it. The sample is typical. The sample size is 140 respondents. Content Validity which refers to the extent to which a measurement reflects the specific intended domain of content. Reliability which refers to the confidence we can place on the measuring instrument to give us the numeric value. If the same set of objects are measured again and again with the same or comparable measuring instrument and the results obtained are the same or similar, then the measuring instrument is said to be reliable. Pilot study was carried out where the draft questionnaire was eventually subjected to pilot testing with a total of 30 consumers, and they were asked to comment on any perceived ambiguities, omissions or errors concerning the draft questionnaire. The feedback received was rather ambiguous thus only minor changes were made. For instance,

technical jargon was rephrased to ensure clarity and simplicity. Data were collected by means of a structured questionnaire, all the items were presented as statements on the questionnaire, with the same rating scale used throughout, and measured on a five point Likert-type scale that varied from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. In the subsequent full-scale survey, data were collected from the insurance consumers who have ULIP Transactions. The data collected will be analyzed and interpreted using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Statistical tools used namely, Simple percentage analysis, Chi-square test and Factor analysis.

Results and Discussions:

Table 1.1

Demographic Variables	Categories	Number of Respondents
Gender	Male	90
	Female	40
Age	18-30	40
	31-40	52
	41-50	19
	51-60	16
	61 and Above	13
Qualification	Upto class 9th	44
	High school	34
	Intermediate	45
	Graduate	16
	Professional	01
Occupation	Govt. Service	11
	Private Service	58
	Self Employed(Professional Services)	14
	Business	36
	Housewife	16
Income	Retired	04
	Upto Rs. 12,000	04
	Rs. 12,001 to Rs. 24,000	36
	Rs. 24,001 to Rs 36,000	42
	Rs 36,001 to Rs 48,001	16
	Rs. 48,001 to Rs 100,000	36
	Rs 100,001 and above	06

7. KMO and Bartlett's Test:

Bartlett's test of sphericity indicates that whether the correlation matrix is an identity matrix which would indicate that the variables are unrelated.

Table 1.2

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.722
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	389.150
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

The significance level (.000) gives the result of the test. Very small values (less than .05) indicate that there are probably significant relationships among the variables. A value higher than about .10 or so may indicate that the data are not suitable for factor analysis.

Table:1.3

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Higher Expected Return than Traditional Plans	1.000	.685
TAX Saving	1.000	.445
Wealth Creation	1.000	.692
ULIPs are Insurance cum Investment Instrument	1.000	.637
Flexibility in choosing Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option	1.000	.949
Liquidity: Option to withdraw/partial withdraw the Fund Value	1.000	.953
Professional Fund Management	1.000	.660
Tiop-up Option: Option to Invest additional in the same Policy	1.000	.574
Saving for Speacial Reason like Children Educcation/Marriage	1.000	.584
Pension Purpose	1.000	.632

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

INITIAL COMMUNALITIES

Initial communalities are estimate of the variance in each variable accounted for by all component or factor.For principal component analysis this is always equal to 1.0(for correlation analysis).

EXTRACTION COMMUNALITIES

Extraction communalities are estimate of the variance in each variables accounted for by the factors. Small values (0.685, 0.445, 0.692, 0.637, 0.953, 0.660, 0.574, 0.584, and 0.632) indicate variables that do not fit well with the factor solution and should possibly dropped from the analysis.

Table:1.4
Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.097	20.974	20.974	2.097	20.974	20.974	2.023	20.229	20.229
2	1.472	14.723	35.697	1.472	14.723	35.697	1.315	13.145	33.375
3	1.125	11.249	46.946	1.125	11.249	46.946	1.238	12.385	45.760
4	1.095	10.952	57.898	1.095	10.952	57.898	1.119	11.187	56.947
5	1.020	10.198	68.096	1.020	10.198	68.096	1.115	11.149	68.096
6	.954	9.537	77.633						
7	.815	8.148	85.782						
8	.709	7.091	92.873						
9	.674	6.740	99.613						
10	.039	.387	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

In the above table principal component analysis is used for the purpose of extracting the data. This table gives Eigen values, variance explained and cumulative variance explained for the factor solution. There are 9 factors or components extracted using **rotated Component Matrix**.

**Table-1.5
Rotated Component Matrix^a**

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Higher Expected Return than Traditional Plans	-.208	.027	.417	.426	.535
TAX Saving	-.018	.335	.183	-.540	-.080
Wealth Creation	.211	-.067	-.049	-.126	.790
ULIPs are Insurance cum Investment Instrument	-.038	-.025	-.782	.015	-.152
Flexibility in choosing Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option	.969	.020	.061	.050	.064
Liquidity: Option to withdraw/partial withdraw the Fund Value	.965	.054	.092	.066	.076
Professional Fund Management	-.031	.771	-.085	-.189	.143
Top-up Option: Option to Invest additional in the same Policy	.104	.138	.026	.728	-.113
Saving for Special Reason like Children Education/Marriage	.192	-.250	.627	-.111	-.281
Pension Purpose	.121	.718	-.062	.210	-.230

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 10 iterations.

Chi-square Test:

Table: 1.6 Age Group (in years) ~ Higher Expected Return than Traditional Plans

Hypotheses: The Relation between age group of the respondent and the Expected rate of return is high

H0: There is no significant relationship between age group and the Expected rate of return.

H1: There is significant relationship between age group and the rate of return

Table-1.6

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.915	16	0.007
Likelihood Ratio	14.863	16	0.006
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.272	1	0.672
N of Valid Cases	140		

a. 18 cells (72.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.02.

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.007) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence the age group has the significant association with the Rate of return.

Table: 1.7 Age Group (in years) * Tax Saving Benefits

Hypotheses: The age group of the respondent and the tax benefits are high

H0: There is no significant relationship between age group and the tax benefits.

H1: There is significant relationship between age group and the tax benefits.

Table-1.7

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.482 ^a	16	0.043
Likelihood Ratio	17.176	16	0.037
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.102	1	0.033
N of Valid Cases	140		
a. 18 cells (72.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .84.			

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.043) which is less than (0.05), hence null

hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence the age group has the significant association with Tax benefits.

Table: 1.8- Age Group ~ Wealth Creation

Hypotheses: To test the relationship between the Age group of respondents and Wealth Creation.

H0: There is no significant relationship between Age Group and Wealth Creation

H1: There is significant relationship between Age Group and Wealth creation.

Table-1.8

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.063 ^a	16	0.025
Likelihood Ratio	19.366	16	0.051
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.529	1	0.219
N of Valid Cases	140		
a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.21.			

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.025) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence, the Qualification has the significant association with Compulsory Investment.

Table: 1.9- Age Group~ ULIPs are Insurance cum Investment instruments

Hypotheses: To test the relationship between the Age groups and ULIPs are insurance cum investment instruments.

H0: There is no significant relationship between Age groups and ULIPs are insurance cum investment instruments.

H1: There is significant relationship between Age groups and ULIPs are insurance cum investment instruments.

Table-1.9

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.822 ^a	16	.018
Likelihood Ratio	14.051	16	.005
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.096	1	.685
N of Valid Cases	140		

a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .56.

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.018) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence There is significant relationship between Age groups and ULIPs are insurance cum investment instruments.

Table-1.11

- Age Group~ Flexibility in choosing investment portfolio/switching the fund option

Hypotheses: To test the relationship between the Age groups and Flexibility in choosing the Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option

H0: There is no significant relationship between Age groups and Flexibility in choosing the Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option.

H1: There is significant relationship between Age groups and Flexibility in choosing the Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option.

Table-1.11

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	45.178 ^a	16	.009
Likelihood Ratio	33.09	16	.008
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.096	1	.685
N of Valid Cases	140		

a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .56.

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.009) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence There is significant relationship between Age groups and Flexibility in choosing the Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option.

Table: 1.12- Age Group~ Liquidity-Option to withdraw or partial withdraw the fund value.

Hypotheses: To test the relationship between the Age groups and **Liquidity-Option to withdraw or partial withdraw the fund value.**

H0: There is no significant relationship between Age groups and **Liquidity-Option to withdraw or partial withdraw the fund value.**

H1: There is significant relationship between Age groups and **Liquidity-Option to withdraw or partial withdraw the fund value. .**

Table: 1.12

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	75.478 ^a	16	.014
Likelihood Ratio	73.09	16	.013
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.089	1	.585
N of Valid Cases	140		
a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .56.			

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.014) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence There is significant relationship between Age groups and Flexibility in choosing the Investment portfolio/Switching the fund Option.

Table: 1.13- Age Group~ Professional fund management.

Hypotheses: To test the relationship between the Age groups and **Professional fund management..**

H0: There is no significant relationship between Age groups and **Professional fund management.**

H1: There is significant relationship between Age groups and **Professional fund management.**

Table: 1.13

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	88.667 ^a	16	.041
Likelihood Ratio	53.09	16	.023
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.877	1	.485
N of Valid Cases	140		
a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .56.			

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.041) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence There is significant relationship between Age groups and **Professional fund management.**

Table: 1.14- Age Group~ Professional fund management.

Hypotheses: To test the relationship between the Age groups and **Professional fund management..**

H0: There is no significant relationship between Age groups and **Professional fund management.**

H1: There is significant relationship between Age groups and **Professional fund management.**

Table: 1.14

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.982 ^a	16	0.009
Likelihood Ratio	15.843	16	0.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.746	1	0.373
N of Valid Cases	149		

a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .56.

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.009) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence There is significant relationship between Age groups and **Professional fund management.**

Chi-square Test:

Table: 1.15 Age Group (in years) ~ Saving for Special Reason like Children Education/Marriage

Hypotheses: The Relation between age group of the respondent and the saving for Special Reason like Children Education/Marriage

H0: There is no significant relationship between age group and t saving for Special Reason like Children Education/Marriage.

H1: There is significant relationship between age group and saving for Special Reason like Children Education/Marriage.

Table: 1.15

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.845 ^a	16	.036
Likelihood Ratio	29.162	16	.023
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.861	1	.243
N of Valid Cases	149		
a. 13 cells (52.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.22.			

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.036) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence the age group has the significant association with the Rate of return.

Chi-square Test:

Table: 1.16 Age Group (in years) ~ Pension

Hypotheses: The Relation between age group of the respondent and Pension.

H0: There is no significant relationship between age group and Pension.

H1: There is significant relationship between age group and saving for Pension.

Table: 1.16

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	45.845 ^a	16	.026
Likelihood Ratio	69.162	16	.033
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.758	1	.253
N of Valid Cases	149		
a. 13 cells (52.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.22.			

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the calculated P value (0.036) which is less than (0.05), hence null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Hence the age group has the significant association with Pension.

CONCLUSION:

- It is clear from factor analysis that the investors or the ULIPs buyers consider 'Higher Expected Return, Tax Benefits, Wealth Creation, Insurance Cum Investment, and Flexibility' more SIGNIFICANT as compared to other five factors viz. 'Liquidity, Professional fund management, Top-up-facility, saving purpose and Pension'. On the basis of Varimax Rotation with Kaiser Normalisation, 5 factors have been extracted. Each factor is constituted of all those variables that have factor loadings greater than 0.5. Eight variables were clubbed into 5 factors. 5 factors were extracted from the 10 variables used in the study. These 5 extracted factors explained 68.09% of the variability the preferences towards ULIPs.
- If we analyze the Total Variance Explained Table and Rotated Component Matrix, we can see the sixth Factor which has Eigen Value of 0.954, (very near to 1), so, if we say that after the five mentioned above factor, the sixth factor which the investors give importance is the feature of Liquidity of the ULIPs.
- The age groups having significant association with the all ten benefits or features of ULIP viz. Higher Expected Return, Tax Saving, Wealth creation, Insurance cum Investment, Flexibility, Liquidity, Professional Fund Management, Top-up-Facility, Saving, and Pension. And the same variables also got loaded in factor analysis, if we analyze the frequency analysis most of them are youth, in age group of (18-30) and 31-40).

Recommendations

For the above stated conclusions the insurance companies need to focus attention on creating confidence among customers about Higher Expected Returns from the ULIPs through good market officering, bring new and innovative products through which investors can avail Tax exemptions benefits, a policy which really create a good and hefty the Fund value.

The Insurance Companies need to educate and bring awareness among customers about the need to invest in the capital market through ULIPs also which give insurance benefits with the opportunity to make the most of the capital market. The insurance companies should run promotional programs to attract more number of customers, education about the need for insurance policy should be educated to them through various strategies like in house company campaigning programs and focused advertisements strategy reaching those focused graduate segment belong to private companies. Insurance companies need to bring awareness and build confidence among consumers about the benefits availed on risk coverage.

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